

Historical geography of the region Naxshab of the early medieval period

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Abstract: In the early Middle Ages, the geographic and political boundaries of Nakhshab region, which connects South Uzbekistan with neighboring countries, toponyms, hydronyms, ethnonyms of the country, changes in the natural environment and processes related to it, the routes of caravan routes, the geographical location of the population, the reasons for the development or crisis of cities and other settlements are covered in this article based on scientific sources and data.

Key words: Tokharistan, Eftali, Southern Sughd, monument Qala'i Zahoki Moron, Erkurgan, Kongyrtog, Olatun railway station, steppe Jom, Chaganiyan, Turkic khanate, monument Shulluktepa, Bahram Chubin, monument Kokhna Fazli.

Today's historical research, in obtaining important results of political, economic and social importance, research in the historical geographical direction is becoming important. Historical geography, which is considered an important component of the science of history, is becoming important in determining the geographical and political boundaries of historical and cultural lands, the reasons for their change, in making scientific conclusions by comparing ancient place names - toponyms, hydronyms, ethnonyms with the current situation, in clarifying the changes in the natural environment and related processes, the routes of caravan routes, the geographical location of the population, the reasons for the development or crisis of cities and other settlements.

In the years of independence in our country, great progress was made in studying the historical geography of the early medieval period of the southern regions of our country. Among the important researches created during this period, it is necessary to mention the fundamental researches dedicated to the Great Silk Road, the works analyzing the works of travelers of the early Middle Ages.

Thus, during this period, the issue of historical geography of Sugdiyana and Tokharistan began to be studied on a new basis, using written sources and archeological data.[1:24] During this period, the scientific knowledge related to the subject under consideration increased significantly. This was a major breakthrough in the study of the subject in question.

The fact that the city of Naxshab in Lower Kashkadarya was one of the residences of the ruler of the Ephthalites led to an increase in the political status of Southern Sughd (the oasis of Kashkadarya). The roads leading from Bukhara and Samarkand Sughd to trade cities in Southeast Iran, Afghanistan and India have passed through the oasis area, and the study of the routes of these caravan routes was important in clarifying the characteristics and boundaries of the location of properties and spaces in South Sughd, as well as the historical geographical location. Therefore, we will briefly touch on them.[2:223]

The roads from Samarkand and Bukhara converged in the large city of Lower Kashkadarya, Naxshab (in the early Middle Ages, after the old city on the site of Erkurgan became a ruin, the center of the oasis moved to the city of Naxshab, where the monument of Qala'i Zahoki Moron was located). In Chinese sources belonging to this period (Beishi) it was called Noshebolo. From this city, they went to the middle reaches of Amudarya (Kelif, Kerki, Burdaliq) or via Subah, Huzor, Temir Darvoza to Termez. [3:74]

One of the main roads leading from Samarkand to the south passed through the present-day Kokdala steppes and the northern slopes of Kongyrtog. In the early Middle Ages, there were

few settlements in this area, mainly the winter residences of nomadic herding tribes, and wells, which were of great importance as important stops on the Samarkand-Naxshab road. At the same time, the information we collected during the study of the ancient roads in the oasis shows that in the steppes between Samarkand and Naxshab, fortifications in the form of large fortifications appeared already in the early Middle Ages. An example of this is the Hazorbuqa and Karatepa monuments located 20 km west of Kokdala. 1.5-2 km from the Samarkand-Karshi railway. [4:103] Hazorbuqa and Karatepa monuments located in the west, near the Olatun railway station, were built in the 70s of the 20th century by academician studied by A.S. Sagdullaev. According to opinion researcher O'. Mavlanov, this is a monument was founded in the III-IV centuries. These monuments were also important as winter residences of local herdsman and important intermediate stops on the Samarkand-Naxshab trade route. The geographical location of these places became important in determining the location, winter residences and pastures of pastoral tribes. [5:98]

The road connecting Samarkand with the international trade centers in the south passed through the Kashkadarya oasis since ancient times. The most important and actively used of them was the Samarkand-Nasaf route. The road from Samarkand to Nasaf through the Jom steppe is divided into several branches here. One direction joined the road from Bukhara and led to Termiz via Subah, Kindik village, Temir Darvoza. The village of Kindik is three days' journey from Nasaf and Kesh, where the trade route from Samarkand through Kesh joins the Nasaf-Termiz trade route. From Samarkand, through Nasaf, they also went to the Amudarya villages (Kelif, Kerki, Amul). [6:233]

From Samarkand, there was also a middle road leading to the Iron Gate and Chaganiyan (Surkhan oasis) through the Jam desert - Chirakchi - Huzar (Guzar) route. Preserved monuments with the names of Oltinboshtepa and Chandaraktepa on the right bank of the middle stream of Kashkadarya it helps clarify the direction.

In Southern Sughd, along the road system leading to the cities of Kelif and Kerki on the left bank of the Amudarya, nine days from Bukhara, craft centers such as Navkad-Kuraish, Altintepa and many villages flourished between Kasbi and Bazda, Iskifagn, Kesh and Naxshab. Research on the historical-geographic location of the finds and monuments confirms that the economic development of the main part of these monuments was primarily organized by agriculture.

Even in the early Middle Ages, transit trade routes connecting Bukhara and Samarkand, the two largest cities of the Turkic Empire with Khurasan and India, passed through the Kashkadarya oasis. The towns and villages along these roads were important in defining the historical geographical boundaries of the oasis. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider these directions.

During this period, many sources provide information about Nasaf, which was considered the capital of the oasis. A new city was founded in Lower Kashkadarya after the Arab invasion of Naxshab in the early Middle Ages. The local people called this city Naxshab, the Arabs named it Nasaf according to their pronunciation. The developed period of the city corresponds to the X-XII centuries. The city of Nasaf (this city became a ruin after the Mongol invasion), according to archaeological research, situated 8 km from Karshi. It was on the site of the Shulluktepa monument in the northwest. In the early Middle Ages, the internal trade route connecting the two main cities of the Kashkadarya oasis - Nasaf and Kesh - passed along the left banks of the Kashkadarya. [7:191]

In particular, Chandaraktepa (beginning of the 9th-13th centuries) was considered an important place that controlled the traffic in Kashkadarya. Zuhratepa, Qamaytepa, Oltintepa, Kishmishtepa and other monuments were studied in this direction.

During this period, the Bukhara-Nasaf route (30 farsakhs) passed through Karachun, Miyankal, Maymurg, and the caravans covered it in 4 days. [8:56]

In Nasaf, the road from Bukhara branched off and it was possible to go to Balkh in the following directions: Nasaf - Subah - Kindik village - Temir Darvoza - Termiz - Balkh or Nasaf - Kelif - Balkh.

To the west of Nasaf are the villages of Kasbi (4 farsakhs) and Bezda (6 farsakhs), which in the early Middle Ages were located on the western borders of the Naxshab estate. [9:56-63] Kasbi is mentioned in Armenian sources as a strong fortress. It is recorded in the sources that Bahram Chubin, one of the famous generals of the Sassanid era, conquered the lands of the Turkic Khanate and subjugated all the "land of the Kushans" from Balkh to the Caspian. [10:86-90]

The city of Bezda, located in the western part of Naxshab, was also one of the important possessions of Southern Sughd. Although there are not enough water sources, it is reflected in the sources that farming has developed in the estates around Bazda, and that the population irrigates crops with well water. The city of Bazda was founded at the beginning of AD. During the period of the Turkish khanate, it was considered one of the important fortifications on the western borders of the Naxshab estate. The distance from Naxshab to Bezda was 40 km. The ruins of this city were on the site of the Kokhna Fazli monument. [11:96-100]

The cities of Kasbi and Bezda, due to their favorable geographical position, played an important role in the system of caravan routes from Bukhara to other trading cities of Termiz, Balkh and Khurasan. [12:1-6] The sources contain information about the caravan route from Bukhara through Kasbi to Termiz, through Bezda to Kelif crossing and Termiz (among which there were intermediate destinations such as Jiken, Old Rabat, Said Well, Bezda, Horan Rabati, Bukhara Village, Khorezm Village and Balkhan). The caravans covered the distance from Bukhara to Bezda in 4 days, and the Bukhara-Kelif road in 5 days. This route greatly shortened the route of trade caravans, saving time and travel costs [13:128-131].

Kashkadarya, which is the main water source of Southern Sugdiyana, and the cities of Kesh, Nakshipa (Ksenipa), Naxshab, Subah in the basin of Guzordarya, which is its left tributary, played an important role in the internal and external economic relations of the oasis. According to the researches, at the beginning of AD, the roads leading from Erkurgan along the right bank of Kashkadarya through monuments such as Beshtepa, Oratepa, Koziboy tepa, Shahri-Khaibar or Karabayr tepa, Payshanba tepa, and the roads leading to Guzor oasis through Nasaf (Shulluktepa), Kafirtepa, Qal'ai Zahoki Moron were used. [14:135-138] During this period, the road connecting Kesh, the capital of Eastern Kashkadarya, with Nakshipa (Yergorgan) became the main link in the internal road system of the oasis.

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